

NOTES

Oxidations of Cis-Dioxalato Diaquo Chromium (III) Complex by Hydrogen Peroxide in Acid Solutions

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Four breaks obtained in the potentiometric titration studies of cis-dioxalato diaquo chromium (III) complex by hydrogen peroxide in different sulphuric acid concentrations, heat treatment and storage show that the oxidation of two oxalato groups takes place in two stages in one electron transfer steps. Compared to oxidations of free oxalic acid with hydrogen peroxide which proceeds slowly only at elevated temperatures in acid solution, co-ordinated oxalate groups are oxidised readily in normal sulphuric acid solution at room temperature. This is suggestive of oxidation occurring while oxalate ligand is bound to the metal ion. Free radical mechanism has been considered to be operative. The formation of peroxy intermediate complex has also been pictured.

The oxidation of oxalic acid by hydrogen peroxide is slow unless the solution is strongly acidic^{1,2}. The review of the literature reveals that no work has been done on the oxidation stages of cis-dioxalato diaquo chromium (III) complex by hydrogen peroxide in acid solutions. The aim of the present investigation³ is to have comparative idea on the oxidations of co-ordinated oxalate and free oxalic acid. Our results indicate that the effect of acid concentrations on the oxidations of co-ordinated oxalate ligand is reverse of the oxidation of free oxalic acid. This leads us to believe that the oxalate ligand is oxidised, while co-ordinated, through intramolecular electron transfer. The oxidation through peroxy intermediate complex appears to be more plausible.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were either of Analar or E. Merck quality. Potassium cis-dioxalato diaquo chromium (III) dihydrate complex was prepared by a published method⁴ and analysed. (Found : Cr, 15.5; $C_2O_4^{2-}$, 51.8. $K[Cr(C_2O_4)_2(H_2O)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$ requires Cr, 15.3; $C_2O_4^{2-}$, 51.9).

The solutions of the oxidant and the complex were prepared in sulphuric acid solutions of the same strength. As the oxidation reaction was very slow, modified⁵ potentiometric titration method was employed.

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2. M. Anbar and H. Taube, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **76**, 6243.
3. Ph.D. thesis of R. N. P. Sinha, March, 1968, Ranchi Univ.
4. K. Alexander. *Inorganic preparations*, Revised edition, 1950, p. 114, London, George Allen and Unwin Ltd., 40 Museum Street.
5. B. P. Gyani and S. N. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 313.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stoichiometry of the reaction can be represented by the equation :

10 c.c. of M/80 dioxalato complex would require 10 ml of M/40 hydrogen peroxide solution for complete redox-reaction. Four breaks corresponding to 2.3 ml, 4.4 ml, 7.4 ml and 10.6 ml have been obtained in the room temperature potentiometric titration curve for normal acid concentration. The stagewise oxidation of the two oxalate groups should show breaks at 2.5 ml ($\equiv 1$ e), 5.0 ml ($\equiv 2$ e), 7.5 ml ($\equiv 3$ e) and 10 ml ($\equiv 4$ e). Our results at room temperature and normal acid concentration are clearly indicative of oxidation occurring through one electron transfer steps. When the solutions are heated at 95° for 2½ hrs. two inflexions at 3.5 ml and 5.05 ml are left. On increasing the acid concentration to 6N, only two vague inflexions at 2.5 ml and 4.4 ml are observed at room temperature. On heating to 95° for 2½ hrs inflexions are nearly suppressed. Further heating does not alter the picture. The reaction mixtures corresponding to the intermediate oxidation stage of oxalate ion were found to initiate the polymerization of vinyl monomers indicating the presence of free radicals.

The probable mechanisms may be suggested through free radical formation and peroxy intermediate complex formation according to the following scheme :

or,

Rest steps same as (5), (6) and (7).

Alternatively peroxide ion may co-ordinate with the dioxalato complex as shown in reaction :

The peroxide ion would then accept electron from Cr(III), which in turn accepts it from the co-ordinated oxalate ion. Dissociation then takes place.

or

The mono oxalato complex would also be oxidised in stages through similar mechanism. The different results at higher temperature may be due to the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide and complete dissociation of the complex to the corresponding mono-oxalato complex with appreciable further dissociation of the mono-oxalato complex into hexa aquo-chromium (III) ion and oxalic acid. At higher acid concentration i.e., 6*N*, the oxidation has been observed to be incomplete and suppressed. This suggests that the alternative mechanism is more probable. At higher acid concentrations hydrogen peroxide would not complex so readily and hence the incompleteness of reactions. The difference in behaviour towards oxidations between free oxalic acid^{1,2} and co-ordinated oxalate indicate that complex formation plays an important role and the ligand reacts while co-ordinated.

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